

A SELF-ALIGNED TEST FIXTURE FOR INTERLAMINAR TENSILE TESTING OF TWO-DIMENSIONAL CARBON-CARBON COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The interlaminar tensile testing of two-dimensional carbon-carbon laminates requires special attention on aligning the specimen with the test fixture. A self-aligned test fixture is designed to efficiently carry out such tests. The self-alignment of the two pull rods of the test fixture is achieved by holding the threaded pull rods by means of a nut prior to gripping the pull rods with the loading frame. It is demonstrated that the fixture can easily be used to measure interlaminar tensile stiffness and strength of thin carbon-carbon specimens. The interlaminar tensile stiffness and strength of three carbon-carbon laminates ($[0/90]_{2s}$, $[0/90/\pm 45]_s$, and $[0/90/\pm 45]_{3s}$) measured by the present test fixture are reported.

1. INTRODUCTION

The carbon-carbon composite material is an emerging high-temperature structural material for application to temperatures well over the capability of any other materials, but the structural application of a two-dimensional carbon-carbon composite is currently limited by its interlaminar tensile properties. To make the two-dimensional carbon-carbon composite a viable structural composite, a great deal of improvement is needed on its interlaminar properties. At the same time we need efficient and reliable test methods to measure these properties in order to monitor the development of the material. The fiber reinforcement in two-dimensional carbon-carbon composites is in the fabric form in the in-plane direction of the composite. Since there is no fiber reinforcement in the thickness direction, the interlaminar tensile stiffness and strength of two-dimensional carbon-carbon are one order of magnitude lower than its in-plane tensile properties. Thus a reliable measurement of the interlaminar tensile strength requires careful design of the test fixture and its alignment.

The carbon-carbon composite material has been in existence over several decades. However, the work found in the literature on characterizing and evaluating its mechanical performance is somewhat limited. There is an ongoing effort by several researchers to quantify the fiber waviness and model the effect of the fiber waviness in the stress-strain behavior of two-dimensional carbon-carbon composites [1-7]. Pollock [8] observed the in-plane tensile failure in plain weave carbon-carbon, and Yurgatis et al [9] evaluated the damage accumulation due to tensile stress in two-dimensional carbon-carbon laminates. Gupta et al [10,11] made failure observations under compression and shear loading. All the work mentioned above focuses mainly on evaluating the in-plane properties of the two-dimensional carbon-carbon composites. Since the fiber reinforcement is in the in-plane direction, the in-plane properties of two-dimensional carbon-carbon are fiber-dominated properties. Because of the presence of matrix cracks and voids, the in situ matrix properties of the carbon-carbon composites are different from the bulk graphite properties. In order to use some sort of micromechanics for the material development, the in situ carbon matrix properties need to be known. Since there is no fiber reinforcement in the thickness direction of the two-dimensional carbon-carbon, the interlaminar properties are matrix dominated. Thus measuring the interlaminar properties (stiffness and strength) of the composite together with proper micromechanics formulae is an indirect and effective way of

determining the matrix properties of the material. In this study, with the designed test fixture, the interlaminar tensile stiffness and strength of three carbon-carbon laminates, $[0/90]_{2s}$, $[0/90/\pm 45]_s$ and $[0/90/\pm 45]_{3s}$, were measured. The laminates were made of 8HS balanced fabric of 3K T300 fiber tows with 24 tows per inch in the warp direction and 23 in the fill direction.

2. FIXTURE DESIGN CONSIDERATIONS

The interlaminar properties of thin carbon-carbon specimens are normally measured by gluing the specimen in between two pull rods. Because of the fiber reinforcement in two orthotropic directions, the in-plane Poisson's ratios of two-dimensional carbon-carbon are very small, approximately 0.01. As a result, gluing of the top and bottom surfaces of the specimen with the pull rods does not induce any significant constraint stresses in the specimen. However, because of the fact that its interlaminar stiffness is one order of magnitude lower than the in-plane stiffness, the test fixture requires careful alignment of its pull rods with the specimen.

In this type of test, the axes of the two pull rods need to be aligned with the specimen centroidal axis. To align the axes of the pull rods with that of the specimen, the normal practice is to glue the specimen in between the two pull rods first, and then machine the rods with the specimen for alignment. This alignment process is expensive and time consuming. In this work a new test fixture is designed in which the axes of the pull rods are self aligned with that of the test frame (e.g., MTS test frame), and the specimen is glued in situ with the pull rods while the pull rods are fixed with the test frame. The self alignment of the pull rods is achieved by holding the two threaded pull rods aligned by means of a nut, while gripping the pull rods with the test frame. The schematic diagram of the test fixture and the components of the fixture are shown in Figures 1 and 2, respectively. The pull rods are of circular cross section, and the ends are gradually tapered to rectangular cross section for direct gripping with the test frame wedge grips. After gripping both the pull rods with the test frame, the pull rods are released from each other by turning the aligning nut up or down over the threads into either of the pull rods. The aligning nut is then eventually removed from the pull rods, and the carbon-carbon test specimen is glued in situ in between the end surfaces of the rods. The gluing surface of the pull rods is made perpendicular to its axis, so that the carbon-carbon specimen is glued between two parallel surfaces of the pull rods. The outer diameter of the threads of the pull rods is made within a tolerance of 0.03 mm of that of the inner diameter of the nut.

3. STUDY OF GLUE PENETRATION IN THE SPECIMENS

It was mentioned before that the top and bottom surfaces of the specimen were glued in situ with the pull rods. A commercial epoxy (Manufacturer: Hartman[®], cure time: 3-5 minutes at 22°C) was used as the glue. Because of the presence of open porosity in the carbon-carbon laminates, the extent of the penetration of the glue in the material needed to be determined. In this case the open porosity was defined as the cracks or voids that were in some way linked to the open surface. The carbon-carbon laminates used in this study had an average open porosity of four percent [12]. The open porosity was measured by impregnating fluorescent dye-mixed resin into a piece of carbon-carbon under pressure. The resin flowed into the cracks and voids that were open to the surface. Slices of the impregnated piece in three orthogonal directions were viewed under a microscope in a fluorescent field to measure the area of the fluorescent resin present on the surface and then to determine the open porosity.

In order to check how much the glue penetrates into the specimen and whether the penetration of the glue into the specimen has any effect on the failure strength, a study was performed to check the extent of the glue penetration into the carbon-carbon specimen. To measure the extent of the glue penetration, the glue used in this study was mixed with a fluorescent dye. Then two pieces of undensified carbon-carbon composites (right after carbonization) with an open porosity of 12 percent were adhered with the fluorescent-mixed glue. Then a through-the-thickness section of the glued piece was taken and polished for optical microscopic observation. Figure 3 shows the microscopic image of the cross section in bright and fluorescent fields. The bright field shows the fiber yarn profile in the composite, and the fluorescent field shows the penetration of the glue into the composite. Comparison of the two images revealed that the extent of the glue penetration is limited to less than a ply thickness. Further, the tested specimens were made of densified carbon-carbon composites whose porosity was three times less than that of the carbon-carbon used in Figure 3. Hence, the glue penetration in the tested specimens was expected to be no more than in Figure 3. Since all the specimens tested were at least eight plies thick, and the failure occurred somewhere at the mid-section

of the specimens, it was inferred that there was no thickness penetration of the glue to the failure surface. On some occasions, however, especially for thin (eight ply-thick) specimens, the glue overflowed at some spots around the edge of the specimen. Fluorescent microscopy of the failure surface, as shown in Figure 4 with 50x magnification, indicated that the radial penetration of the glue was limited to less than 1.5 mm from the edge of the specimen. Examination of the failure surfaces of other specimens revealed that the areal presence of the glue on the failure surface was less than one percent of the failure surface. Thus from the observation of both thickness and radial glue penetration it was inferred that the glue had very little effect on the specimen failure.

4. VALIDATION OF THE TEST FIXTURE

In order to obtain reliable interlaminar tensile strength data, a uniform interlaminar tensile strain is desirable, and bending in the specimen should be minimized as much as possible. Thus to check the strain distribution, the interlaminar tensile strain of the specimen was measured with strain gages installed on the surface of the specimen. Further, to validate the test technique, the interlaminar tensile stiffness of unidirectional graphite/epoxy composite specimens, whose interlaminar stiffness is the same as the transverse stiffness, were measured. The graphite/epoxy specimens used for the stiffness measurements were prepared from a 5-mm (40-ply) thick unidirectional laminate. To have an adequate specimen depth for installing strain gages in the thickness (interlaminar) direction of the laminate, a stack consisting of four blocks of the above laminate was glued together to have specimens of 20 mm in depth. From the glued block specimens of cross section 12.7x6.4 mm were sliced out, keeping the depth of the specimens the same as that of the glued block. The top and bottom surfaces of the specimen were then glued in between the two pull rods to measure the interlaminar stiffness.

To check whether a uniform interlaminar tensile strain distribution in the gage section specimen was achieved or not, the strains on opposite surfaces of the specimen were measured with 0.8128-mm (0.032-inch) strain gages. Also, to assess the effect of the glue line on the measured strain, the strain gages were installed on the surface covering the glue line. The stress-strain curves of the two back-to-back strain gages are shown in Figure 5. The curves in Figure 5 reveal that for a given load, the variation in the strain reading between these two strain gages was about 2.5 percent. This difference may be due to the variation of the glue thickness between the strain gages, bending of the specimen, or error in measuring strains by the strain gages. A microscopic observation of the cross section of the specimen indicated that the thickness of the glue varied between 0.030 to 0.040 mm (14 percent glue thickness variation). After taking into account the stiffness of the glue (4.27 GPa) and the transverse stiffness of AS4/3501-6 graphite/epoxy composite, the variation in the measured strain corresponding to the glue thickness variation is 1.4 percent. Further, a two to three percent error in strain measurement by strain gages is not uncommon. Thus, the variation of measured strains between the two back-to-back strain gages was essentially due to variation in glue thickness and error in strain measurement by strain gages. Hence, the bending in the specimen was practically negligible. Moreover, the measured interlaminar stiffness (corrected for glue thickness) reported in Figure 5 was in good agreement with the transverse stiffness of the material [13].

The specimens used for measuring stiffness, as mentioned before, were prepared from a glued block. In order to study the effect of the glue line on strain measurement, two different strain gages were installed on a specimen. A strain gage of size 3.175 mm (0.125 inch) was installed on the specimen covering a glue line and another one of size 0.8128 mm (0.032 inch) was installed on the composite, not covering the glue line. The measured stress-strain curves from the two strain gages are shown in Figure 6(a). The strain data of the 3.175-mm gage were then corrected for the observed glue thickness of 0.032 mm. The corrected stress-strain curve was essentially the same as that of the 0.8128-mm gage [Figure 6(b)]. For the glue line correction the stiffness of the glue was taken as 4.27 GPa and that for the composite was the measured value by the 0.8128-mm gage. Based on the observations made in Figures 5 and 6, it was inferred that after making proper correction for glue thickness, the interlaminar stiffness of a thin composite laminate can be measured by the present technique.

5. MEASURED INTERLAMINAR TENSILE STIFFNESS

It was mentioned before that in the case of a two-dimensional carbon-carbon composite, the interlaminar stiffness offers a better measure than the in-plane stiffness to characterize the matrix properties. Thus the above technique was used to measure the interlaminar tensile stiffness of the two-dimensional carbon-carbon laminates. Figure 7(a) shows the stress-strain curves of two back-to-back strain gages of size 3.175 mm (0.125 inch) installed on a specimen prepared the same way as

above from the $[0/90/\pm 45]_s$ carbon-carbon laminate. The stress-strain curves are shown to failure. The axial gages were aligned in the thickness direction of the laminate to measure the interlaminar strain, and the transverse gage measured the in-plane strain due to the interlaminar tensile load. The initial interlaminar tensile stiffness of the specimen, corrected for the 0.038-mm glue thickness, was found to be 5.9 GPa (0.857 Msi). The two back-to-back strain gages showed good agreement between each other at the initial loading. They then deviated from each other when the stress-strain curve started showing nonlinearity, which could be due to uneven damage developing about the centroid of the specimen. From the measured transverse strain shown in Figure 7(a), the Poisson's ratio, ν_{31} , of the laminate was found to be 0.01. In addition, to obtain a reasonably good average of the measured interlaminar stiffness, five specimens of the above laminate were tested. The stress-strain curves of three such specimens are shown in Figure 7(b). The measured average initial interlaminar stiffness was 5.05 GPa (0.732 Msi) with a scatter of 12 percent. The interlaminar stiffness of the other two laminates, $[0/90]_{2s}$ and $[0/90/\pm 45]_{3s}$, was measured practically the same as that of the $[0/90/\pm 45]_s$ laminate.

6. MEASURED INTERLAMINAR TENSILE STRENGTH

Instead of specimens of rectangular cross sections, where stress concentrations are expected to occur at four corners of the specimen, the test specimens for measuring the interlaminar tensile strength were made circular in cross section to avoid the corner stress concentrations. In order to have failure somewhere away from the glued surfaces, preferably at the mid-depth of the specimen, the radius of the specimen was reduced symmetrically from the top and bottom surfaces to its mid-depth by 0.5 percent of the radius of the specimen. Three different laminates were tested: $[0/90]_{2s}$, $[0/90/\pm 45]_s$ and $[0/90/\pm 45]_{3s}$. The laminates were made of 8HS balanced fabric of 3K T300 fiber tows with 24 tows per inch in the warp direction and 23 in the fill direction. As a result a representative cell size of the fabric is 8.47x8.84 mm. The diameter of the specimens was chosen as 15.24 mm to include more than a cell of the fabric in the cross-sectional area of the specimen.

With the above test specimen configuration, the interlaminar tensile (ILT) strength of the three laminates mentioned above was measured. All the specimens invariably failed at a ply interface (Figure 8). The measured data are shown in Figure 9. For the eight-ply laminates (thickness of 2.54 mm), $[0/90]_{2s}$ and $[0/90/\pm 45]_s$, the ILT strength did not change due to a change in ply orientation. For the 24-ply laminate, $[0/90/\pm 45]_{3s}$, the measured ILT strength was higher than that of the eight-ply laminates. The cause of this increase was probably due to better control in specimen preparation with the 7.62-mm (24-ply) thick specimens than the 2.54-mm (eight-ply) thick specimens. As stated before, the ILT properties reported in Figures 7(b) and 9 can be used to determine the matrix properties in conjunction with suitable micromechanics formulae.

7. CONCLUSIONS

A self-aligned test fixture for interlaminar tensile testing of thin button specimen was developed. The alignment of the pull rods of the fixture is simple and fast. A technique for measuring interlaminar stiffness of thin woven composite laminates is discussed. To validate the test technique the interlaminar tensile stiffness of unidirectional AS4/3501-6 graphite/epoxy composite laminates was measured. The interlaminar stiffness of AS4/3501-6 laminates measured by this test fixture was found to be the same as its transverse stiffness. It is also demonstrated that both the interlaminar tensile stiffness and strength can easily and efficiently be measured with the test fixture discussed here.

Acknowledgment: This work was sponsored by the WL Materials Directorate under contract number F33615-91-C-5618. The financial support is gratefully acknowledged.

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(a)

(b)

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of the configuration of the test fixture. In view (b) the fixture is turned 90° about its longitudinal axis from view (a).

Figure 2. Components of the test fixture.

Figure 3. The thickness penetration of the glue in a 2D undensified carbon-carbon laminate. The glue is mixed with a fluorescent dye. Magnification: 50x.

Figure 4. The radial penetration of glue in the failure surface of a carbon-carbon specimen. Magnification: 50x.

Figure 5. The interlaminar stress-strain curve of the unidirectional graphite/epoxy (AS4/3501-6) composite specimen measured by back-to-back strain gages.

(a)

(b)

Figure 6. Study of effect of glue thickness on the measurement of interlaminar stiffness of AS4/3501-6 specimens prepared from the glued block.

(a)

(b)

Figure 7. (a) The interlaminar tensile stress-strain curves of $[0/90/\pm 45]_s$ 2D carbon-carbon laminate. The transverse gage was used to measure in-plane strain due to the interlaminar applied load. (b) The interlaminar tensile stress-strain curves of three representative specimens.

Figure 8. View of the failure surface of the carbon-carbon interlaminar tensile strength specimens.

Figure 9. The Interlaminar Tensile (ILT) Strength of Three Different Specimens of 2D Carbon-Carbon